

Need for Integrating Dynamic Line Rating to the Overhead Transmission Lines

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ABSTRACT

Dynamic line rating (DLR) is an overhead transmission line real time monitoring system for monitoring and rating of existing and new overhead transmission lines. DLR sensors are becoming popular with the utilities for optimal use of the line capacity. DLR provides real-time monitoring of conductor temperature, sag, load, and weather conditions. Additionally, provides predictive load model to enhance the efficiency and optimise the line ampacity. The software provided can be used for maximizing the line loading.

The actual current, thermal rating of the line and sag are easily measured using DLR. The sag measurement helps in reviewing ground clearance of the overhead lines in cities, crossings over roads, railroads, other overhead lines, etc. Additionally, measured data like angle (sag) is implemented to the software application to detect ice overloads or fallen trees. Sag cannot be correlated in two similar overhead lines due to various external factors. Higher sag is observed in the older lines.

INTRODUCTION

The existing transmission lines should ensure safe, reliable and assured power delivery. In India, renewable energy sources are being added rapidly and also there is a simultaneous increase in load demand. This calls for additional capacity of the existing lines. In such cases, to deliver assured power, utilities look for new line or uprating of the existing lines.

Today all such measurements are based on Static line rating (SLR). Traditionally, industry relies on the worst-case weather conditions for calculating SLR. This simplifies equipment specification while providing significant safety margin. But it would be wrong to assume the real rating is always greater than the SLR. The maximum utilization of the transmission line is only possible if the operators have accurate data about the actual ground clearance, crossed lines, vegetation, instantaneous conductor temperature, sag and current.

Adding renewable energy sources can cause dynamic current changes on the lines, including direction of power flow changes. Therefore some lines are overloaded and others under loaded. The electricity demands stable and reliable operation in this new condition with the support of smart-grid elements like DLR for real time measurement and data analysis.

If the real conditions of the line are continuously measured in place of SLR, then, more appropriate rating can be considered. This is called in power transmission as Dynamic Line Rating (DLR). The devices used in DLR measure true current, more accurate conductor thermal limits, weather conditions and line sag which is a critical safety need. It has been reported around the world that, the utilities have got benefited by using DLR devices in their network operationally and financially. This is mainly because, utilities can unlock unused transmission capacity, potentially unforeseen impact of contingencies, un-necessary curtailment during forced outages, or not detecting N-1 bottleneck conditions like during wind ramps or even to measure ice loading or tree falling.

Understanding real time changing energy flow, weather conditions in transmission lines is really demanding and complex.

DLR TECHNOLOGY

There are always two different possibilities to increase the ampacity level of the transmission lines. Building new transmission lines or uprate the existing infrastructure. Upgrading with DLR on exiting lines provide realistic data for augmenting the capacity. On the new lines helps in unlocking the additional capacity and helps in taking decision in balancing the network.

DLR technologies have been in service in world utilities since 1977. The products use a variety of physical properties and sensors for both the transmission line and the environment to help define a real time limit which is more appropriate than the commonly used Static Line Rating (SLR). Whereas, traditionally, industry relies on the worst-case weather conditions for calculating SLR.

The assumption underlying SLR is that, the conductor temperature and line sag are deterministically correlated. However, in the field there will be some deviations based on load, age of the line and various site conditions like ambient temperature, wind speed, wind direction etc and hence actual behaviour of the transmission line and capacities must be well established based on dynamic line rating.

The heat transfer of overhead conductor is important to understand to appreciate the fact that DLR is important compared to present day SLR per the below equation;

Relationship between heating and cooling^[6]:

$$P_J + P_M + P_S + P_i = P_C + P_r + P_w$$

P_J - the Joule heating

P_M - the magnetic heating

P_S - the solar heating

P_i - the corona heating

P_C - the convective cooling

P_r - the radiative cooling

P_w - the evaporative cooling

Selecting the right DLR technology and devices

Direct and indirect measurement devices are available for DLR.

The right technology to be selected should be based on physical measurements and not based on mathematical calculations. The most important measurements are current, temperature and sag.

The accuracy of current, temperature, sag, type of alarms is critical while selecting the right sensors. Interlinkage with the SCADA and maintenance of software need to be well understood along with hardware and sensors calibration. The software must be intuitive and open to add different measurements for past and future analysis.

The number of sensors needed depends upon the line length, landscape, critical spans like road crossing or railway crossing or settlement areas etc. If the line is straight and having no change in landscape, then even one device at the lowest clearance from the ground may serve the purpose. Generally, with a line survey, or tower schedule report, it will be easy to suggest the minimum number of sensors needed per line. These devices are easy to install and re-deployable.

The DLR in India, is the most needed on 66kV to 220kV transmission lines due to the rapid increase in load and with the rapid addition of renewable energy sources. These devices are available for higher than 220 kV also.

Kerala Pilot Project Case Study

Sterlite has installed DLR at Cheruthponi dam, Idukki district on VZTP-NDKM-KTPL line at 2300 feet height above sea level. This is a 66kV line and about 40 years old. This line is having different conductors for different sections. The problem statement from KSEB was to review the possible capacity of the line, to connect renewable power generation on this line.

KSEB had done the line survey to identify the longest span on the line with higher sag. The section identified is with ACSR Dog with 680m span. The current on this line today is about 93A -132A and the conductor can be safely loaded up to 324A. One section of the line is having ACSR Mink and hence, the line has got maximum setting for 200A. If this section is uprated, then, the capacity of line may be increased to 300A.

The DLR device was installed in the month of May 2019 and the line is being monitored from then.

The implementation of the DLR sensor has passed through severe rain, thunderstorm, and varying weather conditions and proved to be rugged.

In this case, study is done to see the possible ampacity increase on an existing 40 years old line to utilize the existing assets fully, with additional renewable power connected. The data indicates that the average amperage of the line is 93A. We observed that between 13.00 – 14.00 hours current is about 160A. The recordings are taken for every 10 minutes; hence, it is clear from the graph the current exceeding 150A for a short duration and is not frequently. If the line current goes as high as 160A, the total ampacity on the line that is possible is about 370A from the DLR data.

That means $370 - 160 = 210A$ is the additional ampacity available. This should be always read with weather and wind conditions. The total ampacity can be higher or lower depending upon wind speed, direction and solar irradiation etc.

This data along with complete line survey (e.g. hotspot survey) if done then actual ampacity and capacity is possible to predict. The graph clearly indicates that if a section of Mink is re-conducted then, line capacity can be enhanced. Hence, connecting renewable energy source to the same line may be a possibility.

Advantages of Using DLR Device

DLR usage has got many advantages like; congestion relief before CAPEX is approved for uprating, Improved grid reliability, capacity curtailment, faster integration of renewable, after re-conductoring to help review the enhanced capacity and savings in CAPEX and OPEX, understanding the capacity and planning needs.

The implementation challenges

There is a need to promote such devices by the utilities with good regulatory environment. This unlocks additional capacity on the existing asset or helps in network planning on the new line.

CONCLUSION

Transmission line capacity can be fully utilised, and reliability can be increased by using DLR devices across the lines. The DLR is a simple device, easy to install and reusable.

Understanding the transmission line real time data brings in intelligence and helps in faster decision making. It is good to consider DLR as part of the CAPEX.

Digitisations of the lines using DLR helps in CAPEX and OPEX optimisation. Before submission for CAPEX approval for any line, the real time data, study and recommendations based on that will support to take the right decision. The same when installed on the new lines, help in understanding the additional available capacity and planning.

Acknowledgement

KSEB for giving an opportunity for doing a pilot project.

Matej Kovač, OTLM for mentoring.

Madan Gopal Yadav, Manager, Rakesh Shankar, AVP, Sterlite Power for support rendered for the project work.

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